

Transition Temperatures and Mesophase Identification of Two Homologous Series of Anils

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Two series, each comprised of fourteen homologs were prepared by condensing 4-*n*-alkoxybenzaldehydes with 4-ethylaniline and 4-*n*-butylaniline respectively. The homologs were purified and transition temperatures were studied by differential thermal analysis and phase contrast microscopy. The tentative assignments of mesophases by texture observation are presented. Plots of transition temperatures *vs* carbon numbers in the chain are given. The mesomorphic to isotropic transition points for even homologs constitute a 'wave shaped' curve while for the odd homologs, a rising curve is found. The smectic-nematic transition curve is a rising one but slightly concave and unlike other series it coincides with the nematic-isotropic curve for odd homologs.

L IQUID crystalline compounds exhibiting mesophases in the vicinity of room temperature would provide ease in studying molecular arrangements and physical properties of the mesophases. With this view, 4-*n*-alkoxybenzylidene-4'-ethylaniline series (I) and 4-*n*-alkoxybenzylidene-4'-*n*-butylaniline series (II) were synthesised. Tables 1 and 2 present the transition temperatures while Figures 1 and 2 are the plots of transition temperatures *vs*. number of carbon atoms in the alkoxy chain for these two series. Some homologs of these series were reported during the compilation of this data¹⁻³.

Observation

In 4-*n*-alkoxybenzylidene-4'-ethylaniline series, the low temperature smectic phase of C₄-, C₅-, C₆-, C₇- and C₉- homologs is mosaic in appearance but gives

TABLE 1. 4-*n*-ALKOXYBENZYLIDENE-4'-ETHYLANILINE SERIES

Alkyl Group	Temperature (°C) of transition to			
	R-O-C ₆ H ₄ -CH=N-C ₆ H ₄ -C ₂ H ₅			
	Smectic ₂	Smectic ₁	Nematic	Isotropic
1. Methyl	—	—	(32.5) ^a	56.5
2. Ethyl	—	—	63.5	69.0
3. <i>n</i> -Propyl	—	—	(47.0) ^b	67.5
4. <i>n</i> -Butyl	—	41.0	51.0	67.0
5. <i>n</i> -Pentyl	—	49.5	54.5	59.0
6. <i>n</i> -Hexyl	—	41.0	58.0	68.5
7. <i>n</i> -Heptyl	52.5	57.0	62.5	67.0
8. <i>n</i> -Octyl	57.0	62.0	70.5	72.5
9. <i>n</i> -Nonyl	(64.0)	64.5	—	73.5
10. <i>n</i> -Decyl	57.0	65.5	—	76.5
11. <i>n</i> -Dodecyl	60.5	67.5	—	78.0
12. <i>n</i> -Tetradecyl	(69.0)	70.0	—	77.5
13. <i>n</i> -Hexadecyl	(69.0)	(74.0)	—	75.5
14. <i>n</i> -Octadecyl	—	(67.5) ^b	—	78.5

^a Values in parentheses indicate monotropy.

^b Values obtained by extrapolation of the respective curves.

TABLE 2. 4-*n*-ALKOXYBENZYLIDENE-4'-*n*-BUTYLANILINE SERIES

Alkyl Group	Temperature (°C) of transition to				
	Smec-tic ₃	Smec-tic ₂	Smec-tic ₁	Nema-tic	Iso-tropic
1. Methyl	—	—	—	20.0	47.0
2. Ethyl	—	—	—	35.5	79.0
3. <i>n</i> -Propyl	—	—	—	39.5	56.0
4. <i>n</i> -Butyl	—	—	36.5*	45.5	73.5
5. <i>n</i> -Pentyl	—	24.0	50.5	51.5	68.5
6. <i>n</i> -Hexyl	34.0	57.0	58.5	69.5	77.5
7. <i>n</i> -Heptyl	36.0	62.0	63.5	74.5	76.5
8. <i>n</i> -Octyl	40.0	64.5	68.0	—	82.0
9. <i>n</i> -Nonyl	50.5	67.5	70.5	—	82.5
10. <i>n</i> -Decyl	40.0	68.5	73.0	—	85.0
11. <i>n</i> -Dodecyl	52.5	71.5	76.0	—	86.5
12. <i>n</i> -Tetradecyl	—	60.0	77.0	—	85.0
13. <i>n</i> -Hexadecyl	—	65.5	77.5	—	83.5
14. <i>n</i> -Octadecyl	—	74.5	78.5	—	81.5

* Smectic₁-Smectic₂ transition as the compound is room temperature smectic.

a new kind of X-ray diffraction pattern suggesting that the structure of this phase is different from any smectic mesophase structure known so far. The structure observed by phase contrast microscopy for this smectic mesophase is that of a gross mosaic differing from the appearance of smectic B materials. The individual mosaic "blocks" are more

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elongated, generally, with parallel blade-like structures and significantly larger than the individual blocks observed for smectic B materials.

When various transition temperatures for both the series are plotted vs number of C-atoms in the alkoxy chain, the change mesomorphic to isotropic for even

Fig. 1. 4-n-Alkoxybenzylidene-4' ethylanilines

In 4-n-alkoxybenzylidene-4'-n-butylaniline series, smectic₁ phase of hexyloxy to dodecyloxy homologs and smectic₂ phase of butyloxy and pentyloxy homologs are modified smectic B as described above.

homologs is represented by a "wave-shaped" curve i.e. in the initial stage the curve falls, then gradually rises, levels off and then falls. The mesomorphic-isotropic transition temperatures for odd homologs

Fig. 2. 4-n-Alkoxybenzylidene-4' n-butylanilines

lie on a rising curve which coincides with the falling curve for even homologs. The smectic-nematic curve joining all the homologs is rising one but slightly concave and unlike other series, coincides with the nematic-isotropic curve for the odd homologs. Smectic₁-smectic₂ and smectic₂-smectic₃ transition temperatures for all the homologs lie on smooth curves.

Discussion

The wave shape of the mesomorphic-isotropic transition for even homologs suggests that the terminal cohesions in these series are weakened at lower temperatures by thermal vibrations in the lower homologs but as the series is ascended, the increasing lateral cohesions support the terminal cohesions to maintain molecular order over a higher temperature range. As the molecule gets elongated, the terminal attractive forces become less effective, consequently the mesomorphic-isotropic transition is likely to be guided by lateral attractions. This argument however does not explain the rising nature of the curve for odd homologs. The difference in the two curves may probably be due to the differences in the molecular packings arising from terminal methyl groups of the alkoxy chain for odd and even homologs.

The absence of mesomorphism in propyl homolog of series I is conspicuous as the preceding members are nematic while the succeeding ones are both smectic and nematic. The melting point (67.5°) of this homolog is also not unusually high for mesophase formation as the tetradecyl and hexadecyl homologs are mesomorphic though their melting points are higher than that of propyl ether. The lack of mesomorphism in octadecyl ether of the same series is likely due to its highest melting point in this particular series.

The smectic-nematic transition points for all the members lie on a slightly concave curve which coincides with the nematic-isotropic curve for odd homologs. The smectic phase connected with this transition in series I for C₄-, C₅- and C₆- homologs (smectic B) and for C₇- and C₈- homologs (smectic A) is different. Similarly smectic phase for C₄- and C₅- ethers of series II is mosaic in texture while fan-shaped for C₆- and C₇- ethers.

Experimental

p-Ethylaniline, *p*-*n*-butylaniline and *p*-anisaldehyde are commercially available and were used without purification.

p-*n*-Alkoxybenzaldehydes: They were prepared by modification of Williamson synthesis reported for 2-*n*-butyloxynitrobenzene⁴. A mixture of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (0.1 mole), alkylbromide (0.11 mole), anhydrous K₂CO₃ (0.1 mole) and 2-butanone (70 ml) was refluxed under stirring for 24–48 hrs. Afterwards water (500 ml) was added and the layers were separated. The aqueous layer was extracted with benzene (4×75 ml). The benzene extract and the organic layer were combined and washed with 75 ml

of 15% caustic soda solution. The mixture was then dried over sodium sulfate, the solvent was stripped and the aldehyde portion was fractionated under reduced pressure. Yields ranged from 50 to 70%.

Schiff's bases: Equimolar quantities of the aldehyde and aniline were mixed and refluxed in absolute ethanol for about 15 min. The resulting products were recrystallised several times from ethanol to constant transition temperatures. Low melting homologs were recrystallised from *n*-hexane; the solution in hexane was cooled to 0° and the precipitates were filtered rapidly. A representative selection of the anils was submitted to elemental analysis to check purity and composition. Table 3 presents a summary of these analyses.

Determination of Transition Temperatures: The melting and transition points were determined both by Leitz Ortholux Polarising Microscope equipped with a Mettler FP-2 heating stage and differential thermal analysis (Du Pont DTA 900). The differential thermograms were recorded at a heating rate of 10°/min and sensitivity of 0.1°/min. The sample used for differential thermal analysis was approximately 5 mg and the atmosphere of nitrogen was maintained. The temperatures recorded in Tables 1 and 2 are from DTA charts—the error of the temperature measurements is estimated to be smaller than ±2°.

TABLE 3. ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS

Code No.*	Molecular Formula	C%		H%		N%	
		Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
I-3	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ ON	80.92	80.92	7.86	7.99	5.23	5.17
I-4	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ ON	81.12	80.98	8.18	8.29	4.98	4.95
I-5	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ ON	81.36	81.42	8.47	8.35	4.75	4.66
I-6	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ ON	81.54	81.66	8.74	8.69	4.53	4.62
I-14	C ₃₅ H ₅₁ ON	83.01	83.10	10.69	10.70	2.94	2.82
II-3	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ ON	81.36	81.45	8.47	8.36	4.75	4.74
II-6	C ₂₃ H ₃₁ ON	81.90	81.97	9.20	9.17	4.15	4.13
II-8	C ₂₅ H ₃₅ ON	82.19	82.17	9.59	9.43	3.84	3.81

* Code numbers are the Table and Compound Numbers separated by a dash.

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